

THE IMPORTANCE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: In this article, the importance of independent education in ensuring the quality of education in higher education institutions, the organization of independent education, the formation of their independent thinking, the knowledge, skills, and qualifications necessary for independent performance of academic work in students and the issues of organization, development, and increase of students' activity in activities outside the auditorium are highlighted. **Key words:** credit, education, independent education, quality, knowledge, skills, competence, opinion, development.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НЕЗАВИСИМОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение самостоятельного образования в обеспечении качества образования в высших учебных заведениях, организации самостоятельного образования, формировании у них самостоятельного мышления, знаний, умений и квалификации, необходимых для самостоятельного выполнения учебной работы у студентов и студентов. освещены вопросы организации, развития и повышения активности студентов в деятельности вне аудитории.

Ключевые слова: кредит, образование, самостоятельное образование, качество, знания, умения, компетентность, мнение, развитие.

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim sifatini ta'minlashda mustaqil ta'limni ahamiyati, mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish, ularning mustaqil fikrlashlarini shakllantirish, talabalarda o'quv ishlarini mustaqil bajarishda kerak o'ladigan bilim, ko'nikma, malaka va kompetensiyalarini tashkil topishi, rivojlanishi, talabalarning auditoriyadan tashqari ishlardagi faolliklarini oshirish masalalari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kredit, ta'lim, mustaqil ta'lim, sifat, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, kompetensiya, fikr, rivojlanish.

In the "Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017, higher education based on the competitiveness of national personnel and global practice Consider joining the Bologna Declaration of June 19, 1999, which promotes the improvement of the quality of the national education system, the mutual recognition

of diplomas of the countries participating in the Bologna Process, and the implementation of teacher and student exchange programs. is broken.

It is fundamental in the social, economic, political and spiritual life of our country changes are happening. The adoption of the new version of the Law "On Education" is especially important in reforms in the field of education. The development or, on the contrary, the crisis of each country depends on the level of improvement of the education system in the country. This indicates that almost all higher education institutions in the country will start operating in the credit-module system in the coming years. Also, life itself requires the implementation of reforms in all spheres of our country, changing people's worldview, training mature and up-to-date specialists. In the republic, great importance is attached to strengthening the education system and harmonizing it with the requirements of the times. In this case, it is important that the system of training, education and upbringing of specialist personnel is closely connected with the demands of reforms. Training of specialist personnel who can meet the requirements of the time, improvement of education and all its structural structures based on the requirements of the State is one of the urgent issues before us. In this program, credit education systems in foreign countries, innovative methods of organizing educational processes based on the credit system and ensuring its quality, activities of pedagogues in the credit-module system, methodological support of the educational process in the credit-module system, training legal documents related to the field of education and their content, legal and moral-educational foundations of preventing and fighting corruption in educational institutions, normative legal foundations of higher education are described.

In the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847, the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education, the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and independent thinking are qualitatively new. promotion, modernization of higher education and development of social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies as strategic issues. For example, in the Concept "increasing the share of independent education hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, educational the task of directing the process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, the wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on international educational standards into the educational process.

Resolution No. 824 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" and Higher and secondary special education was developed on the basis of the minister's order No. 311 of July 16, 2021 "On approval of state educational standards of higher education".

It is also emphasized that students can acquire the necessary competences of specialists through independent education, independent work, continuous improvement of their skills, development of creative creativity, research, and logical thinking. The organization of the educational process plays an important role in the training of specialist personnel. Currently, in the curricula, the ratio of classroom (contact) and independent education of students is from 40/60 percent to 50/50

percent in undergraduate education, from 30/70 percent to 50/50 in master's specialties. allocated to the percentage ratio. In the process of changing the educational program, a number of issues and problems of science should be studied through independent education. Independent education is the independent acquisition by students of a part of the program materials in one or another subject.

One of the main tasks of higher education is to direct the specialist to self-development, to increase his knowledge independently, to develop his innovative activity and creative personality. It is not enough to give ready knowledge to the student by the teacher for the implementation of such a task. Such a way turns the student into a passive consumer of learning. However, today we need not a passive learner in the acquisition of knowledge, but an active creator of it. The result should be such that the future specialist has any theoretical and be able to express the practical problem, find the most appropriate and appropriate results, and prove their correctness, which will be able to scientifically or methodically analyze the ways to solve it. Changes in the education system are closely related to the content of education. Updates also require thinking about new forms and methods of organizing student learning. In this sense, the organization of students' independent work is not only an important form, but to be an important part that forms the basis of the educational process requires. All this involves acquiring modern teaching methods, developing students' creative abilities, taking into account the opportunities and potential of each student, moving from group studies to individual studies. This process should be organized in such a way that as a result of it, the ability, skills and qualifications of the student to learn independently and apply this knowledge to life are formed.

The main goal of students' independent work in the credit module system is the organization and development of students' knowledge, skills, competences and competencies necessary for independent performance of educational work.

Tasks of students' independent work	Expected result
To search for new information to perform independent work determine the necessary measures	Analyzes several literatures for independent work
Use of information resources in the process of independent work	Doing independent work analyzes and edits information sources in the process
Working with normative documents, scientific-methodical materials, educational literature	Learns to work with normative documents, scientific-methodical materials. Get acquainted with newly published scientific and educational literature related to the field. Membership level of students in the

	information-library center increases
Working with electronic educational literature and databases	Uses information resources remotely in OTM information-library centers
Preparing work plans for examination, processing them according to expert opinion, creating conditions for systematic and creative execution of work	Prepares work plans for examination, processes defects and errors according to the expert's opinion, gets used to systematic, regular and time-based execution of work

According to the standard of time established for students' independent work organizational forms, independent work options and independent performance tasks are developed for all subjects in the departments, they are discussed and approved in the scientific-methodological council of the faculty and at department meetings.

Organizing students' independent work means defining the goals and tasks of each, developing guidelines or methodical recommendations, and selecting scientific literature in order to compile a list of themes and forms of its methodical support.

Independent education is a systematic activity aimed at forming theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies based on independent learning of educational material, assignments of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience.

Independent education is a form of education aimed at strengthening acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, additional information or independent study of material.

Independent work is an active method of education that solves the educational task assigned by the teacher and under his guidance. Independent work is the organization and implementation of concrete activities of students in connection with the set goal. The student's independent work is characterized by his high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative, and timely and perfect completion of all tasks.

So to speak, all activities aimed at educating the future specialist's way of thinking form their basis. Any type of training that allows the student's independent thinking to be born, to increase his cognitive activity, is closely related to independent work.

Self-directed learning should not be understood as the reduction of assignments and workloads, leaving students to their own devices, but as interactive independent activities of students regularly guided by teachers. The role of independent education in improving the quality of the educational process is great. The student must understand that independent education is carried out in his interest. In fact, the concept of a student's independent work refers to his set of independent work that is carried out in the classroom and outside the classroom, under the guidance of the teacher or without the participation of the teacher. Under what conditions is independent work carried out:

1. Directly in the audience - lecture, practical training, seminar or in the process of giving tasks on laboratory work.

2. One-on-one with the teacher outside the class schedule in giving advice during communication, in the process of creative communication, in the execution of a single task in the elimination of indebtedness, etc.

3. During the performance of educational or creative tasks by the student in the library, at home, in student houses, in departments.

The boundaries between these types of work are not too strict and can easily cross over into each other. It is worth noting that independent work of students can be both in the auditorium and outside it. Independent work outside the auditorium is the main focus.

Therefore, independent work and classroom training complement each other, increase the knowledge and professional competence of students.

Factors of students' interest in independent work.

Active independent work of students can take place only if there are serious and stable interests. The most serious factor in this is the preparation of future pedagogues for future effective professional activity. Let's consider the internal factors that allow students to activate their independent work:

1. The usefulness of the work being done. If the student knows that the results of his work can be used in the course of a lecture, in a methodical guide, in laboratory work or in practical training, in the preparation of articles, his attitude towards the work he is doing will change dramatically for the better, as well as the quality of the work. increases. Accordingly, the student should be mentally prepared for such work, the necessity of the work to be performed should be shown.

2. Student's participation in creative activities. It can take many different forms. In particular, scientific research works, artistic works, methodical works, etc. conducted by the departments.

3. Participation in science olympiads, scientific-research works, practical work contests, etc.

4. Use of factors of interest in knowledge control (rating, tests, non-traditional exam forms, etc.). These factors create a spirit of competition in appropriate situations. This very situation forms and develops the student's inner need to work on himself, to develop himself.

5. The fact that enough time is allocated during the educational process to the content and forms of organizing independent work also allows students to activate their independent work. The ratio of independent education in today's higher education institutions established on the basis of the credit-module system is from 40/60 percent proof to 50/50 percent ratio in undergraduate education, from 30/70 percent ratio to 50/50 percent independent ratio in master's specialties. the organization of independent work is defined in the curriculum intended for work. It can be seen that enough time is allocated for independent work. The main thing is to use this time effectively and efficiently.

There are two main directions of organizing the educational process based on the independent work of students

1) Increasing the role of independent work in audience training. To do this, professors and teachers are required to develop methods and forms that ensure a high level of independence and quality of preparation of students in the organization of classroom training.

2) To increase the activity of students in independent work in all areas outside the auditorium. Problems in increasing students' activity in activities outside the classroom are associated with a number of difficulties. It can be seen that not only many students, but even some professors and teachers are not ready to do independent work. This is often manifested in a professional or

psychological direction. In addition, poor quality information provision can be added. In many cases, information supply is not at the level of demand, as a result of which there is a decrease in efficiency. Also, we can add the lack of self-confidence in students and the lack of well-developed speech culture among the factors that cause them not to actively participate in independent education.

The main task in organizing students' independent work is to create psychological didactic conditions for the development of intellectual initiative and thinking in any form of training. The main principle in the organization of student independent work should be to ensure that students move to individual work. In this case, it is important to move some tasks from formal and passive performance to conscious and active performance. The goal of students' independent work is to teach them to work independently first with educational content, and then with scientific information, to form the basis of self-direction and development, and then to regularly improve their skills. The role of the teacher is performed by the teacher. It should always be in the center of attention that he is working not with the student in general, but with a specific person. It is desirable for him to know his student's strengths and weaknesses, to take into account his individual abilities and interests. The task of the teacher is to see and increase the good aspects of the student - the future highly qualified specialist. When studying any subject, three interrelated forms of organizing students' independent work are noticeable:

1. Independent works outside the auditorium.
2. Independent works in the Auditorium. It is organized directly under the guidance of the teacher.
3. Creative form can be extremely diverse. Including: analytical information, lectures and written works on the given subject related to separate chapters of the subject being studied.

It would be appropriate to give the student the right to choose the subject, even the supervisor;

- preparation of illustrative materials on the chosen subject, in which the topic is given by the teacher, its content and form, performance is determined by the student;
- composing scientific crosswords, the size, complexity, and content of which are formed by the student himself;
- to the scientific monograph of a modern scientist, to the work of a writer his own personal based assessment, separating the main ideas and rules and write a review with a recommendation for use;
- performing homework of various nature. This includes exercise and solving problems, translating or retelling a text, selecting and studying literary or scientific sources, making various tables, performing graphic work, performing various calculations, etc.;
- performing individual assignments aimed at developing student initiative and independence. Individual assignments can be received by each student or a group of students;
- performing course work, graduation qualification work;
- scientific-theoretical or scientific-practical conferences, examinations, preparations for Olympiads;
- writing a scientific essay on the chosen topic.

In order to form and develop a positive attitude towards students' independent work, the specific goals and tasks of the work should be explained at each stage, and students' understanding of these goals and tasks should be monitored. These works later become the basis for the formation of the skills and abilities of the student to independently set tasks and choose goals. Equal half of practical

sessions, that is, 50% of a pair, should be spent on independent performance of problems and exercises.

Organization of independent education of students should serve to successfully solve the following tasks:

- implementation of independent educational activities in connection with the goal of acquiring competencies that allow students to develop themselves, obtain independent knowledge and form innovative activities;
- independent acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, problem to educate a creative person who is able to formulate and find optimal ways to solve it;
- creation of students' motivation to learn the curriculum;
- to increase the responsibility of students to acquire knowledge; - to enable students to develop general cultural and professional competencies;
- creating conditions for students to acquire independent knowledge, self-management and self-development.

Summary. There are many forms and methods of organizing education for students. Which of these to choose and use depends on the subject, the goals and tasks of the teacher, as well as his experience and skills. Independent education is directed to activities based on students' high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative and timely and perfect completion of all tasks.

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